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Current applications of the sonogashira reaction in the synthesis of heterocyclic compounds: An update

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Abstract

The Sonogashira cross-coupling reaction involves the coupling of terminal alkynes with aryl or vinyl halides in the presence of a Pd and a Cu(I) co-catalyst. We tried to reveal the importance of the applications of the Sonogashira reaction in the synthesis of heterocyclic compounds. The reactions occur under relatively mild conditions and tolerate a wide variety of functional groups.

Keywords: Sonogashira, palladium, Pd-catalyzed, Cu-catalyzed, Cu-free, 2-Formyl/acetyl-N-substituted pyrrolo [2,3-b] quinoxaline, H-Pyrazolo [5,1-a] isoquinolines, name reaction.